

COMPARATIVE AND TYPOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE TOTEM "MOON" IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the comparative typological features of the "moon" totem in English and Uzbek literature, recreates its archaic features based on literary sources. The components of the concept "Moon" are presented in the form of typological features, which are analyzed in the literary aspect. Observations about the ambivalence of ideas about the moon in English and Uzbek literature are substantiated.

Language is an integral part of culture, its tool. The language of the people is not only a tool for communication and influence, but also a means of assimilating culture, receiving, storing and transmitting culturally significant information. "The individual is unique as a biological and psychological individual, but he is born into a ready-made world. Thus, the child already belongs to his society, his era and culture. The developing personality will have to live in accordance with the explicit and implicit models and patterns adopted in this culture. Language is a special way of existence of culture, a factor in the formation of a picture of the world: "the selection of images and their linguistics is the result of cultural and literary interpretation of the fragments of reality themselves in order to express an attitude

towards them - value or emotionally significant."

The cognitive approach to the study of the semantics of a word lies in the study of the very meaning of the word, in which not only the signs necessary and sufficient for identifying the signified are fixed, but also naive knowledge about the signified. Such an integrated approach to the study of the conceptual structure makes it possible to reconstruct the concept through its linguistic expression.

All concepts have fixed and free forms of expression in the language, which have limitations in compatibility; "one of the most important theses, comprehended in the framework of cognitive linguistics, is that it is the concept that determines the semantics of the linguistic means used to express it." All those properties that are comparatively typological features are not

the proper properties of objects as such, because they are not described in the literature. They correspond only with the reflection of the real world in language, that is, with what is commonly called linguistic comparison.

The first comparison of the basic structural components of the concepts moon and moon presents a description of the main groups of structural comparative-typological features of the concepts under study. Motivating, conceptual, evaluative and symbolic features of the concepts moon and moon are described in separate concepts. Authoritative etymological and explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek and English languages, as well as dictionaries of symbols are widely used as sources of research material.

The second comparison of the development of the structures of the concepts moon and moon analyzes the figurative signs of inanimate nature on the basis of elements, substances, food, subject signs, figurative signs of wildlife, signs of character, occupation, emotional and mental signs, social, including ethical signs. Each paragraph contains tables that reflect the quantitative data identified during the study and the features of the analyzed concepts that form their structures.

In English etymology, the word moon is interpreted as a formation from the Old High German **tapo** "moon", Latin **mensis** "month": "Middle English tope, from Old English tope; akin to Old High German **mano** moon, Latin **mensis** month, Greek men month, mine moon. As pointed out in Webster's Revised Unabridged Dictionary, the word moon may have been derived from the root meaning "measure", it was the moon that was used to measure time. In turn, in dictionaries, month goes back to the Uzbek oh- "month", and, as

etymologists note, it expresses the idea of variability, change. This idea actualizes the motivating attribute 'variability', which is expressed by the lexemes alter and alteration, fickle, transfigured, change, abide, growing, lessening/lesser, small, tiny, waste, increase, magnify, turn, become.

The "Big Encyclopedic Dictionary" notes another conceptual feature of the moon - the phases of the luminary, which also refers to the scientific picture of the world: "the phases of the moon are successive changes during the month of the visible shape of the moon.

The collected linguistic material showed that the structures of the concepts luna and moon include two more features that are not marked with the corresponding semes in explanatory dictionaries: the phase of the season of the year and location above a certain locality/city/country/cardinal direction.

The structures of the concepts of the two languages **oy (uzbek)** and **moon** consist of motivating, evaluative, symbolic, figurative signs of inanimate nature and in literature they consist of elements, matter, food, artifacts; ethical groups of signs. One can speak about the universal and national components of the structures of concepts in the concept sphere of one or another ethnic community. Universal in the structures of the concepts under study will be motivating signs, part of the conceptual signs of a celestial body, a satellite of the earth, a luminary. Figurative signs have many discrepancies.

In the conclusion of the work, the results of the study are summarized, a conclusion is made about the quantitative representation of certain groups of features in the structures of the studied concepts, the most frequent, as well as

common and differentiating features in the structures of the studied concepts are identified.

Thus, the structures of the studied concepts are formed by the same groups and subgroups of features; however, their quantitative representation differs, as well as the presence of some features in the studied concepts. The ways of verbalization of signs in the described groups and subgroups in the structures of these concepts also differ.

The conducted research has its own perspectives. The unexplored area includes the corresponding concepts in German, French, Italian, Chinese and other concept spheres. Of particular interest are the concepts of the moon and moon in the author's pictures of the world of individual poets and writers. The concepts of moon and moon can be analyzed from the standpoint of a psycholinguistic associative experiment.

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